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MEHANIZMI VANPROCESNE ZAŠTITE MALOLETNIH SVEDOKA U REPUBLICI SRBIJI

Raspoloživost svedoka koji želi da dà iskaz pred organom postupka, kao i kvalitet njegovog svedočenja, je od suštinske važnosti za sve sisteme krivičnog pravosuđa koji su u skladu sa međunarodnim standardima poštovanja ljudskih prava, konkretno sa pravom na pravično suđenje utvrđeno članom 6 Evropske konvencije za zaštitu ljudskih prava i osnovnih sloboda. Nedostatak materijalnih dokaza, kao i nedostatak dovoljno odvažnih i hrabrih svedoka, organu postupka umnogome otežava sprovođenje krivičnog postupka i kažnjavanje učinioca najtežih krivičnih dela. Zbog važne uloge svedoka, prilikom procesuiranja organizovanog kriminaliteta i drugih težih oblika kriminaliteta, a sa druge strane i velike opasnosti koje svedočenje nosi po život i zdravlje svedoka i njemu bliskih lica, a naročito ako se uzme u obzir činjenica da se u toj ulozi može naći i maloletnik, nateralo je države sveta da pored mera procesne, usvoje i mere vanprocesne zaštite svedoka. Iz tog razloga i Republika Srbija je 2005. godine predvidela pored procesne i vanprocesnu zaštitu svedoka donošenjem Zakona o policiji i Zakona o programu zaštite učesnika u krivičnom postupku. Ovim zakonskim aktima uspostavljen je sveobuhvatni okvir za obezbeđivanje bezbednosti, psihološkog integriteta i spremnosti svedoka, posebno maloletnika, da sarađuju sa pravosudnim sistemom bez straha od odmazde ili sekundarne viktimizacije.

Ključne reči: zaštita svedoka, maloletni svedoci, vanprocesna zaštita, Zakon o policiji, Zakon o programu zaštite učesnika u krivičnom postupku.

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MECHANISMS OF EXTRAPROCEDURAL PROTECTION OF JUVENILE WITNESSES IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

The availability of a witness willing to provide a testimony before a judicial or prosecutorial authority, as well as the quality and credibility of such testimony, is of fundamental importance for all criminal justice systems that adhere to international standards of human rights protection. This particularly refers to the right to a fair trial guaranteed under Article 6 of the European Convention on Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms. The absence of material evidence, along with a lack of sufficiently courageous and reliable witnesses, significantly hinders the work of competent authorities in conducting criminal proceedings and imposing relevant punishment for the perpetrators of the most serious criminal offenses.

Given the crucial role of witnesses in the prosecution of organized crime and other grave forms of criminality, as well as the serious risks that testifying may entail for the life and safety of witnesses and their close relatives, states worldwide have been compelled to adopt not only procedural safeguards but also extra procedural measures for witness protection. These measures are particularly important in cases where the witness is a minor. In line with global trends, the Republic of Serbia introduced extra procedural witness protection mechanisms in 2005, thus supplementing the existing procedural safeguards through the adoption of the Police Act and the Act on the (witness) Protection Program for Participants in Criminal Proceedings. These legislative acts established a comprehensive framework aimed at ensuring the security, psychological integrity, and willingness of witnesses, particularly minors, to cooperate with the justice system without fear of reprisal or secondary victimization.

Keywords: witness protection, juvenile witnesses, extra procedural protection, Police Act, Act on the Protection Program for Participants in Criminal Proceedings.